

NEANIAS
**Novel EOSC services for Emerging Atmosphere,
Underwater and Atmospheric Challenges**

Deliverable

Deliverable: D3.9 Atmospheric Thematic Services Assessment Report

31/08/2022

NEANIAS is funded by European Union under Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme via grant agreement No. 863448.

D3.9 Atmospheric Thematic Services Assessment Report

Document Info

Project Information			
Acronym	NEANIAS		
Name	Novel EOSC Services for Emerging Atmosphere, Underwater & Atmospheric Challenges		
Start Date	1 Nov 2019	End Date	31 Oct 2022
Program	H2020-EU.1.4.1.3. - Development, deployment and operation of ICT-based e-infrastructures		
Call ID	H2020-INFRAEOSC-2018-2020	Topic	H2020-INFRAEOSC-2019-1
Grant No	863448	Instrument	RIA
Document Information			
Deliverable No	D3.9		
Deliverable Title	Atmospheric Thematic Services Assessment Report		
Due Date	31-Aug-2022	Delivery Date	25-Oct-2022
Lead Beneficiary	UBIWHERE		
Beneficiaries (part.)	NKUA, ATHENA, UNIMIB, MEE0, NOA		
Editor(s)	Noela Pina (UBIWHERE)		
Authors (s)	Noela Pina (UBIWHERE), Ricardo Vitorino (UBIWHERE), Alessandro Tibaldi (UNIMIB), Spyridon Rapsomanikis (ENTA-ATHENA)		
Contributor (s)	Nikos Chondros (NKUA), Michalis Konstantopoulos (NKUA), Noemi Corti (UNIMIB), Sofia Bressan (UNIMIB), Olyna Gounari (NKUA), Alekos Falagas (NKUA), Makis Ntouskos (NKUA), Vasilios Tsironis (NKUA), Antonia Kournopoulou (NKUA), Konstantinos Karantzalos (ATHENA)		
Reviewer(s)	Kovács József		
Workpackage No	WP3 - Atmospheric Research Services		
Version	V1.0	Stage	Final
Version details	Revision: 1. Last save: 2022-10-25, 04:24 Pages: 34. Characters: 40.183		
Distribution	Public	Type	Report
Keywords	Services, Atmospheric, Astrophysics, Planetary Science, Validation, Testing, Feedback		

Change Record

Version	Date	Change Description	Editor	Change Location (page/section)
1.0	2022-10-25	Document version submitted to EC	Noela Pina	

Disclaimer

NEANIAS is a Research and Innovation Action funded by European Union under Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme, via grant agreement No. 863448.

NEANIAS is project that comprehensively addresses the ‘Prototyping New Innovative Services’ challenge set out in the ‘Roadmap for EOSC’ foreseen actions. It drives the co-design, delivery, and integration into EOSC of innovative thematic services, derived from state-of-the-art research assets and practices in three major sectors: underwater research, atmospheric research and atmospheric research. In each sector it engages a diverse set of research and business groups, practices, and technologies and will not only address its community-specific needs but will also enable the transition of the respective community to the EOSC concept and Open Science principles. NEANIAS provides its communities with plentiful resource access, collaboration instruments, and interdisciplinary research mechanisms, which will amplify and broaden each community’s research and knowledge generation activities. NEANIAS delivers a rich set of services, designed to be flexible and extensible, able to accommodate the needs of communities beyond their original definition and to adapt to neighboring cases, fostering reproducibility and re-usability. NEANIAS identifies promising, cutting-edge business cases across several user communities and lays out several concrete exploitation opportunities.

This document has been produced receiving funding from the European Commission. The content of this document is a product of the NEANIAS project Consortium and it does not necessarily reflect the opinion of the European Commission. The editor, author, contributors and reviewers of this document have taken any available measure in order for its content to be accurate and lawful. However, neither the project consortium as a whole nor the individual partners

that implicitly or explicitly participated in the creation and publication of this document may be held responsible for any damage, financial or other loss or any other issue that may arise as a result of using the content of this document or any of the project outputs that this document may refer to.

The European Union (EU) was established in accordance with the Treaty on the European Union (Maastricht). There are currently 28 member states of the European Union. It is based on the European Communities and the member states’ cooperation in the fields of Common Foreign and Security Policy and Justice and Home Affairs. The five main institutions of the European Union are the European Parliament, the Council of Ministers, the European Commission, the Court of Justice, and the Court of Auditors (<http://europa.eu.int/>).

Table of Contents

Document Info	2
Change Record	3
Disclaimer	4
Table of Contents	5
Tables of Figures & Tables	6
Abstract	7
1. Introduction	8
1.1. Context	8
1.2. Content and rationale	9
1.3. Structure of the document.....	9
2. Assessment Process overview	10
2.1. User Assessment Methodology.....	10
2.2. User Assessment rounds	10
3. Atmospheric Thematic Services Assessment Use Cases and User Forms	12
3.1. A1 – ATMO-FLUD.....	12
3.2. A2 – ATMO-STRESS and ATMO-SEISM	14
3.2.1. <i>ATMO-STRESS</i>	14
3.2.2. <i>ATMO-SEISM</i>	16
3.3. A3 – ATMO-4CAST	18
4. Atmospheric Services Assessment and User Feedback Results	20
4.1. Atmospheric Services User Assessment.....	20
4.2. Atmospheric Services User Feedback	21
4.2.1. <i>A1 – ATMO-FLUD</i>	21
4.2.2. <i>A2 – ATMO-STRESS</i>	24
4.2.3. <i>A2 – ATMO-SEISM</i>	26
4.2.4. <i>A3 – ATMO-4CAST</i>	29
5. Summary	32
References	33
List of acronyms	34

Tables of Figures & Tables

Table 1 User Assessment Methodology for each service release.	10
Table 2 User Assessment rounds for each service release.	10
Table 3 Series of webinars organized by WP3 NEANIAS Atmospheric and to collect user feedback and service assessment.	11
Table 4 Number of end users and results of the evaluation on the use cases to assess the NEANIAS ATMOSPHERIC Services releases (release #1, #2 and #3).	20

Abstract

This document is a final overall report on the assessment and evaluation of the NEANIAS Atmospheric services from user perspective. Assessment and evaluations processes have been performed for each of the Atmospheric services release cycles (from release #1 to the latest release #3) involving users both internal to the NEANIAS consortium but also external to the consortium mainly belonging to academic and research institutes. Also, user feedback has been collected through user feedback forms.

1. Introduction

1.1. Context

The NEANIAS WP3 “Atmospheric Thematic services” is focused on the co-design of four services in the atmospheric environment, addressing land-atmosphere interfaces, appropriate for the Research, Development and Business user-communities. The atmospheric services will deliver a springboard of tools to enrich the workflows of a wide range of targeted users from academic/research institutions and industrial stakeholders, e.g. engineering of air pollution control systems and related technology companies, and also end-users at national institutional level such as Civil Protection Agencies. Interest can arise also from more regional governmental institutions such as Regions and Municipalities, especially in relation to detection and evaluation of atmospheric anthropogenic or natural pollutants releases in the atmosphere. Conversely, the quantitation of their man made or natural sinks.

The first service A1, named FLUD, provides the users the ability to calculate atmospheric fluxes of Energy and Green House Gases across the terrestrial and oceanic interfaces, using the “Eddy Covariance” method and related algorithms (A1 ATMO-FLUD service). Explained in detail in the documentation that accompanies this service, are the fundamental scientific principles that support this method, the limitations that apply for these calculations and the format of the data input.

The A2 Service comprises two services: one named “ATMO-STRESS”, calculates the trajectories of tectonic stress based on a series of local data of stress, and presents them as a map (stress field). It permits the input of any data related to stress, spanning from earthquake focal mechanism solutions to stress calculated from fault slip data sets to geotechnical measurement of in-situ stresses. The second service, named “ATMO-SEISM”, compares a series of parameters regarding the seismicity of a region and the variation of gas emission in the atmosphere, in order to find possible correlations. It automatically produces a series of graphs that correlate all the possible parameters, spanning from latitude and longitude of earthquakes, their foci, their depth, magnitude, distance from the point of gas measurement, gas concentrations, etc.

Finally, the A3 service, named “ATMO-4CAST” provides users the ability to obtain and visualize meteorological, road emissions and air quality simulation and forecasts based on their own datasets. The service can receive different types of data and the necessary model parameters and, passing them through popular models such as WRF-ARW, QTraffic and AUSTAL2000, visualize the obtained outputs (e.g., a map with a visualization of the forecasted air temperature). Such a service is useful for users who have their own datasets and play key roles on meteorological, road transport or air quality domains.

Services and software development plan as well as the validation strategy have been guided by Task 3.1 “Atmospheric sector user requirements, service co-design and gap analysis” and outcomes of Deliverables D3.1 [1] and D3.2 [2]. The Atmospheric Services now reached release #3 and a most mature stage TRL8. All the testing and quality assessment has been crucial in reaching this maturity and has been performed within task T3.5 “Atmospheric sector testing & assessment”.

1.2. Content and rationale

This deliverable, D3.9, is a report containing the details of the testing and assessment processes performed on the Atmospheric Research Services for each of the release cycle from release #1 to the latest release #3 [3-8].

The service assessment has been performed thanks to assessment rounds involving users both internal to the NEANIAS consortium but also external to the consortium, mainly belonging to academic and research institutes. Furthermore, user feedback have also been collected.

1.3. Structure of the document

This document is organized as follows. In chapter 2, we present a general overview of the NEANIAS Atmospheric services assessment. In the following chapter, we present the use cases and forms (Chapter 3). Chapter 4 reports the user assessment and feedback for each atmospheric service. Finally, in Chapter 5 we conclude this report with a summary of the atmospheric services assessments.

2. Assessment Process overview

2.1. User Assessment Methodology

The user assessment and validation has been performed initially through the definition of a list of Use Cases with all defined steps (for Release #1), and later through User feedback forms available in each service platform. The adoption and integration of these forms was different for the Atmospheric services. Therefore, Table 1 presents for each release the methods chosen by atmospheric services.

Specifically for Release #1, use cases were defined per service in a document file, with additional step-by-step guides detailing the use of the services. The document with the use-case also served for collecting the feedback of the user, which was then aggregated and reported in the corresponding Deliverable 3.4 [4].

Table 1 User Assessment Methodology for each service release.

Atmospheric Service	Release#1	Release#2	Release#3
A1 ATMO-FLUD	Use case definition (with specific test steps and expected results)	Nextcloud forms, integrated with the service	Nextcloud forms, integrated with the service
A2 ATMO-STRESS	Use case definition (with specific test steps and expected results)	Nextcloud forms, integrated with the service	Nextcloud forms, integrated with the service
A2 ATMO-SEISM	Use case definition (with specific test steps and expected results)	Nextcloud forms, integrated with the service	Nextcloud forms, integrated with the service
A3 ATMO-4CAST	Use case definition (with specific test steps and expected results)	Use case definition for weather module	Google forms in the first validations. Later, the Nextcloud forms were integrated in each module of the service.

2.2. User Assessment rounds

User assessment rounds to collect information regarding services validation and assessment together by any feedback from the user point of view have been performed for each service release and one additional assessment has been performed before the mid-term review and included in Release #2.

Table 2 User Assessment rounds for each service release.

Atmospheric Services Releases	Production date	User assessment round
-------------------------------	-----------------	-----------------------

D3.9 Atmospheric Thematic Services Assessment Report

Atmospheric Thematic Services Release #1	18/11/20	From Nov to Dec 2020
Atmospheric Thematic Services Release #2	12/10/21	From Jun to Oct 2021
Atmospheric Thematic Services Release #3	01/07/22	From Mar to Jun 2022

Additional validation sessions have been linked to the webinars organized for each of the services and reported in the following table.

Table 3 Series of webinars organized by WP3 NEANIAS Atmospheric and to collect user feedback and service assessment.

ATMOSPHERIC Service	Webinar Title (Local)	Date
A2 ATMO-STRESS	<i>ATMO-STRESS: Geo datathon (Milano, Italy)</i>	March 28th 2022, 08:30 CET
A3 ATMO-4CAST	<i>RAISE YOUR VOICE TOWARDS SUSTAINABILITY (Aveiro, Portugal)</i>	March 15th 2022, 12:00 CET
A3 ATMO-4CAST	<i>ATMO-4ALL: Presenting the new cloud-based air quality estimation service (Aveiro, Portugal)</i>	May 19th 2022, 19:00 CET
A1 + A2 + A3	<i>NEANIAS ATMO WORKSHOP (Xanthi, Greece)</i>	June 3th 2022, 8:00 CEST
A1 + A2 + A3	<i>NEANIAS ATMO WORKSHOP (Athens, Greece)</i>	June 28th to 29th 2022
A1 + A2 + A3	<i>NEANIAS OPEN INNOVATION WORKSHOP (Athens, Greece)</i>	September 5th 9:00 CEST

3. Atmospheric Thematic Services Assessment Use Cases and User Forms

This chapter reports on the established use cases and user feedback forms to assess the Atmospheric Services from the user perspective.

3.1. A1 – ATMO-FLUD

[ATMO-FLUD](#) is the NEANIAS service for calculating Flux Densities of momentum, energy and scalars, e.g., for monitoring greenhouse gases flux densities. It provides two distinct algorithms, depending on the kind of data that is available: Eddy Covariance for fast (10Hz) data, and Gradient method for slow (1Hz) data but with sensors at multiple heights. These algorithms were already published at the peer-reviewed literature.

This service is now integrated with all needed core services, such as AAI for handling authentication and authorization, logging for tracing the execution towards customer support, accounting for measuring the service’s usage, file sharing (Nextcloud) for handling users’ files, and with the monitoring services of WP7 and EOSC for monitoring the service’s availability and reliability. Furthermore, the helpdesk is handled via the NEANIAS Service Management System (SMS).

The service is available interactively at the above URL, while a web API is also provided to allow for programmatic reuse. [Documentation](#) is also available online for both the U/I and the API. Furthermore, we prepared a [video](#) and posted it on YouTube so that end-users can get a quick overview of the service’s operation.

After the first release, a validation round was prepared with specific use-cases, that were distributed via email along with the following feedback form:

NEANIAS A1 ATMO-FLUD Validation TEST LOG

Project Name:	NEANIAS ATMO-FLUD	Validation Designed by:	S. RAPSOMANIKIS rapso@athenarc.gr
Module Name:	ATMO-FLUD	Designed date:	26 th November 2020
Release Version:	1.0.0	Validation Executed by:	<Validator name>
Dependencies:	None	Date of Execution:	<Validation date>
Requirements	Availability of test data (ensured by validation designer)		
Service access/download	Service: https://atmo-flud.dev.neanias.eu Documentation: https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/a1-service		

Use Case#	UC-ATMO-FLUD-0001
Description	Running flux densities with direct upload
Preconditions	available data should be uploaded only by user

D3.9 Atmospheric Thematic Services Assessment Report

Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
Log in	User logged on	Pass/Fail	
Send data to service	Data submitted	Pass/Fail	
Submit execution parameters	Algorithm started execution	Pass/Fail	
Monitor algorithm execution	Algorithm finished	Pass/Fail	
View result in the browser	UI task	Pass/Fail	
Download results	File downloaded to user's computer	Pass/Fail	
Use case result	Pass/Fail		
General comments			

Starting from the second release and going forward, we integrated Nextcloud forms for feedback and created one form for each algorithm, so that we can aggregate user feedback at a fine grain.

The hyperlinks for the forms are the following:

- [Eddy Covariance](#)
- [Gradient method](#)

For example, the one for Eddy Covariance is this:

- What is your level of expertise in the micro-meteorology domain? *
 - Pre-grad student
 - Post-grad student
 - Phd in the area
 - Expert
- How was your experience using our web interface? *
 - 1 (Poor)
 - 2 (Bad)
 - 3 (Average)
 - 4 (Good)
 - 5 (Excellent)
- Please provide your comments on the web interface (if any)
- How satisfied are you with the results? *
 - 1 (Poor)
 - 2 (Bad)
 - 3 (Average)
 - 4 (Good)

D3.9 Atmospheric Thematic Services Assessment Report

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 5 (Excellent) ● Please provide your comments on the results (if any) ● Was the time to produce the results reasonable? * <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 1 (Poor) ○ 2 (Bad) ○ 3 (Average) ○ 4 (Good) ○ 5 (Excellent) ● How satisfied are you with the presentation of the results? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 1 (Poor) ○ 2 (Bad) ○ 3 (Average) ○ 4 (Good) ○ 5 (Excellent) ● Please provide your comments on the presentation of the results (if any) ● In what format would you like your results to be delivered? (e.g. *.dat, *.csv, *.txt) ● Why did you choose to use our service? * ● Please provide your general comments you have on our service (if any) ● If you are accessing this service as part of a class, please enter here your student id and name
--

3.2. A2 – ATMO-STRESS and ATMO-SEISM

3.2.1. ATMO-STRESS

Atmo-STRESS is a service that has been implemented in the framework of NEANIAS to produce maps of tectonic stress trajectories based on a series of local stress data. The core functionalities of ATMO-STRESS were based on the LISSAGE software (Lee & Angelier, 1994 [9]). User authentication and authorization is handled by the NEANIAS AAI service (C2). Logging and Accounting are handled by the corresponding NEANIAS services (C2). The service is also integrated with the NEANIAS file sharing service for handling user files and file sharing. An API is also offered for use from other NEANIAS services.

After the 1st release, the test case (TEST-ATMO-STRESS-0010) was defined and users could give their feedback with the following TEST LOG template.

NEANIAS A2 ATMO-STRESS Validation TEST LOG (release#1)

Project Name:	NEANIAS Atmospheric Thematic Services	Software Designed by:	Olympia Gounari olympia_g@live.com Makis Ntouskos mdouskos@gmail.com
----------------------	---------------------------------------	------------------------------	---

D3.9 Atmospheric Thematic Services Assessment Report

Module Name:	ATMO-STRESS	Software Designed date:	11/2020
Release Version:	1.0	Test Executed by:	<Validator name>
Dependencies:	<LIST-DEPENDENCIES>	Date of Execution:	<Validation date>
Test Requirements	Internet access: required Input file: .txt format Restrictions: field separator = comma, decimal point = dot Input dataset should contain the following fields: 1) Point geographic coordinates in WGS'84 (epsg:4326) Coordinate Reference System 2) Azimuth of horizontal stress axis direction for each point (0-360 degrees) Input dataset field names should be "Lat" for latitude, "Lon" for longitude and "Azimuth" for azimuth angle.		
Service access/download	Service access: https://atmo-stress.neanias.eu/ Service documentation: https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/a2-1-service/en/latest/		

Test Case#	TEST-ATMO-STRESS-0010		
Test Description	<Test description>		
Preconditions	<Precondition for test, e.g., previous test complete>		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
1 Upload -or choose an existing- file		Pass/Fail	
2 Select "Polynomial" or "Distance Weighted" method		Pass/Fail	
3 Select "Order" parameter		Pass/Fail	
4 Optional. Set "k", "p", "R" values		Pass/Fail	
5 Select "Output type"		Pass/Fail	
6 Compute maps		Pass/Fail	
7 Download result	.zip file containing: three file formats (.shp, .kml, .geotiff) compatible with GIS environments, result's quick preview (.png) and an execution report (.json)	Pass/Fail	
Test result	Pass/Fail		
General Comments			

For the 2nd and the last release, Atmo-stress was also validated and users gave their feedback through the following form: <https://files.neanias.eu/apps/forms/MCLjeFRHS7H6NGmJ>

D3.9 Atmospheric Thematic Services Assessment Report

Also, the following links were crucial for user's validations:

- Service documentation: <https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/a2-1-service/en/latest/>
- Videos: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=VdO5lOcOd1Y>
- User guide: https://citegr.sharepoint.com/:w:/r/teams/h2020-neanias/_layouts/15/Doc.aspx?sourcedoc=%7B81321A42-B140-4DF1-91BE-C304E4B1E148%7D&file=Atmo-stress_guide.docx&action=default&mobileredirect=true

3.2.2. ATMO-SEISM

[ATMO-SEISM](#) is a service that has been implemented in the framework of NEANIAS to help end-users which are more experienced in scripting/programming, to explore and discover possible correlations between the seismicity of a region and the variation of gas emission in the atmosphere. ATMO-SEISM has been developed as a Jupyter Notebook service hosted in a dedicated JupyterHub deployment. The ATMO-SEISM service, with the use of a developed Python Package (pyradon), enables users to comparingly process and analyze gas releases and earthquake datasets and plot useful visualizations. User authentication and authorization is handled by the NEANIAS AAI service (C2). Logging and Accounting are handled by the corresponding NEANIAS services (C2). The service is also integrated with the NEANIAS file service for handling user files and file sharing.

After the 1st release, two test cases (TEST-ATMO-SEISM-0010 and TEST-ATMO-SEISM-0011) were defined, and users could give their feedback with the following TEST LOG template.

NEANIAS A2 ATMO-SEISM Validation TEST LOG (release#1)

Project Name:	NEANIAS Atmospheric Thematic Services	Software Designed by:	Alekos Falagas alek.falagas@gmail.com Makis Douskos mdouskos@gmail.com
Module Name:	ATMO-SEISM	Software Designed date:	11-2020
Release Version:	1.0	Test Executed by:	<Validator name>
Dependencies:	-	Date of Execution:	<Validation date>
Test Requirements	Internet access		
Service access/download	Service access: https://atmo-seism.neanias.eu Service documentation: https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/a2-2-service		

Test Case#	TEST-ATMO-SEISM-0010
Test Description	Login and uploading of a data set related to gas measurements and earthquake data

D3.9 Atmospheric Thematic Services Assessment Report

Preconditions	None		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
1 Open Service and login	A successful login with NEANIAS SSO Identity provider to the service	Pass/Fail	
2 Upload data to Jupyter Hub	Data successfully uploaded to the server	Pass/Fail	
Test result	Pass/Fail		
General Comments			

Test Case#	TEST-ATMO-SEISM-0011		
Test Description	Open jupyter notebook example and process the uploaded data (.csv files)		
Preconditions	Previous test complete		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
1 Import python packages	Successful import	Pass/Fail	
2 Open data with pandas	Reading data as pandas dataframes	Pass/Fail	
3 Preprocess data	Clear pandas dataframes from NAN values and coordinates are also validated	Pass/Fail	
4 Modelling	A prediction function and a R2 score is printed in console	Pass/Fail	
5 Plotting	A series of plots regarding the gas measurements and earthquake measurements combined	Pass/Fail	
Test result	Pass/Fail		
General Comments			

For the 2nd and the last release, Atmo-seism was also validated and users gave their feedback through the following form: <https://files.neanias.eu/apps/forms/M7N8bLZMgis6f92n>

Also, the following links were crucial for user's validations:

- Service documentation: <https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/a2-2-service>
- Videos: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=VdO5lOcOd1Y>
- User guide: https://citegr.sharepoint.com/:w:/r/teams/h2020-neanias/_layouts/15/Doc.aspx?sourcedoc=%7B79F55D5A-C087-451F-9389-70FD4DCB98BC%7D&file=Atmo-seism_guide.docx&action=default&mobileredirect=true

D3.9 Atmospheric Thematic Services Assessment Report

3.3. A3 – ATMO-4CAST

The [ATMO-4CAST](#) service delivers a novel cloud-based solution that aims to allow the prediction of air quality on an urban scale. This service is divided into three modules: Weather forecast based on the WRF model; Simulation of traffic emissions based on the QTraffic model [10]; Local/urban scale air quality simulation based on the AUSTAL2000 model [11].

In both first releases, only the Weather module was developed. Therefore, for the first validations the use case (UC-ATMO-4CAST-0001) was defined and users could give their feedback with the TEST LOG template.

NEANIAS A3 ATMO-4CAST Validation TEST LOG (release#2)

Project Name:	NEANIAS Atmospheric Thematic Services	Software Designed by:	Luís Coimbra lcoimbra@ubiwhere.com
Module Name:	ATMO-4CAST	Software Designed date:	September 2021
Release Version:	2.0	Test Executed by:	<Validator name>
Dependencies:	None	Date of Execution:	<Validation date>
Test Requirements	Internet connection. Input data available in: https://files.neanias.eu/s/M235gyfdFrKrtbN or select directly in service page using demo files option		
Service access/download	Service access: https://atmo-4cast.neanias.eu/ Service documentation: https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/a3-service/en/latest/		

Test Case#	UC-ATMO-4CAST-0001		
Test Description	Generate a simulation by uploading input data and visualise results		
Preconditions	None		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
Log in	User logged in.	Pass/Fail	
Initiate new study	New study page with a description of the different input methods and a radio button form.	Pass/Fail	
Select input files format (GRIB or JSON) or demo files option	A new form is displayed with fields for a name, description and input data depending on the choice of the previous step: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Grib format (GRIB data, Vtable, WPS configuration and WRF configuration files); JSON format (configurations and matrices files). 	Pass/Fail	
Submit test files	The page redirects to the detail page of the study that was just created. It shows a table with the stages of the simulation, an empty table of output files and a table with	Pass/Fail	

D3.9 Atmospheric Thematic Services Assessment Report

	the input files provided which are available to be downloaded.		
Monitor algorithm execution	Check the progress in the task table. As the simulation executes, the several steps update automatically (Running / Finished).	Pass/Fail	
Navigate to past studies listing	Table with a listing of the past studies of the user and their status. This table is searchable and sortable.	Pass/Fail	
When finished, check the results and navigate the preview images	Cycle through the several preview images of the output.	Pass/Fail	
Download any output file	The output table contains PNG, JSON and netCDF files. The download starts after pressing the download button.	Pass/Fail	
Test Case result	Pass/Fail		
General Comments	(Please, at least, indicate your choice of input method)		

In the last release, the emission and air quality modules were already available in the service. Thus, they were also validated and users gave their feedback through the following forms:

- Google Form (for 3 modules):
https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1sgS5C9ELXWte0qywgdhrgqllti_imulwFiypKhadl3M/prefill (used before creating forms in the service)
- Forms integrated in the service:
 - Weather module - <https://files.neanias.eu/apps/forms/imyooaaZkX7XKqWf>
 - Emission module - <https://files.neanias.eu/apps/forms/LBXA9EnezskGy3wi>
 - Air Quality module - <https://files.neanias.eu/apps/forms/SjYEaPYWTkFpeNnm>

Also, the following links were crucial for user's validations:

- Service documentation:
<https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/a3-service/en/latest/index.html>
- Videos:
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=8JeTt9iQ0Ss&t=70s>
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=sv8ysZbmHJs&t=3s>
- User guide:
https://citegr.sharepoint.com/:w:/r/teams/h2020-neanias/_layouts/15/Doc.aspx?sourcedoc=%7BF866A3F6-1C5B-4D41-B9B8-B725F0D9FD14%7D&file=Atmo-4Cast%20-%20User%20guide%20-%20AirQuality.docx&action=default&mobileredirect=true

4. Atmospheric Services Assessment and User Feedback Results

4.1. Atmospheric Services User Assessment

The following table summarizes the information on the validation of the Atmospheric Services releases (#1, #2 and #3) and includes: the number of end users validating the service and the evaluation percentage on passed/failed use cases.

Table 4 Number of end users and results of the evaluation on the use cases to assess the NEANIAS ATMOSPHERIC Services releases (release #1, #2 and #3).

Atmospheric Services	Release #1		Release #2		Release #3	
	# Users	Evaluation	# Users	Evaluation	# Users	Evaluation
ATMO-FLUD	12	100% PASSED	85	179/200 successful executions (90%)	37	All executions were successful (100%)
ATMO-STRESS	7	100% PASSED	13	78/80 successful executions (97.5%)	65	88/90 successful executions (97.8%)
ATMO-SEISM	5	44% PASSED 66% FAILED	6	24/46 successful executions (52%)	13	50/76 successful executions (66%)
ATMO-4CAST	6	100% PASSED	9	32/46 successful executions (70%)	68	96/122 successful executions (80%)

All the validation procedures for each service and the results of the validation by end users have been collected according to the method reported in Section 2. Furthermore, the detailed validation is reported on Deliverable 3.4 [4], 3.6 [6] and 3.8 [8].

Overall feedback from the first releases, especially release #1, were mainly addressed to the improvements on the UI of the atmospheric services. After the improvements on this front, the services could continue improving on the methods used to integrate input data, infrastructure utilization and on the outputs (especially their formats).

At the first validation round, the ATMO-FLUD service got feedback from the users about impediments in data upload, due to poor connectivity and/or large files. Because of this, we improved the service's input methods to allow consumption of data available at a public URL, greatly enhancing the user experience in this case, which proved popular in the use of our

D3.9 Atmospheric Thematic Services Assessment Report

service. Thanks to our upfront design of a user-friendly U/I, with progressive feedback to the user about the execution status, we never got any complains on this front. Because of this, all further improvements were focused on better utilization of the infrastructure and the integration with needed core services for the service to become available at EOSC.

From the first validation round, A2 services were improved thanks to users' feedback: more in detail, ATMO-STRESS user interface was improved, and errors in the results were fixed following the suggestions of the users. Thanks to these improvements, we reached a high degree of satisfaction at the 3rd and final validation round. Regarding ATMO-SEISM, from the first validation new outputs were added, and some graphic aspects of the outputs were improved following users' feedback. For this service, the percentage of successful executions at the 3rd and final validation round is lower (66%), mostly due to the fact that the service is designed for people who are experienced in scripting/programming.

Since the first validations, ATMO-4CAST service received recommendations to improve the UI and also some users could not understand the amount of inputs necessary to run the service. Therefore, both UI and documentations of the service was improved, which was shown in the improvement of validation results. Although both ATMO-4CAST new modules (emission and air quality modules) were available only for the third round of validations, the positive results of the validations and their implementation in two of the NEANIAS Business cases demonstrate the usability of these modules.

4.2. Atmospheric Services User Feedback

All the details regarding the received user feedback for all Atmospheric Services can be found on the previous deliverables regarding the Atmospheric services validation.

4.2.1. A1 – ATMO-FLUD

At the time of this writing, ATMO-FLUD has accumulated the following feedback as reported by the Nextcloud Forms software. Please note we omitted long text responses for brevity.

For Eddy Covariance:

80 responses

Summary Responses

What is your level of expertise in the micro-meteorology domain?

- 53 (66%): Pre-grad student
- 17 (21%): Post-grad student
- 5 (6%): Phd in the area
- 4 (5%): Expert
- 1 (1%): What is your level of expertise in the micro-meteorology domain?
- 0 (0%): No response

D3.9 Atmospheric Thematic Services Assessment Report

How was your experience using our web interface?

- 35 (44%): 5 (Excellent)
- 31 (39%): 4 (Good)
- 11 (14%): 3 (Average)
- 3 (4%): 2 (Bad)
- 0 (0%): No response
- 0 (0%): 1 (Poor)

How satisfied are you with the results?

- 39 (49%): 5 (Excellent)
- 31 (39%): 4 (Good)
- 9 (11%): 3 (Average)
- 1 (1%): 2 (Bad)
- 0 (0%): No response
- 0 (0%): 1 (Poor)

Was the time to produce the results reasonable?

- 34 (43%): 5 (Excellent)
- 29 (36%): 4 (Good)
- 14 (18%): 3 (Average)
- 3 (4%): 2 (Bad)
- 0 (0%): No response
- 0 (0%): 1 (Poor)

How satisfied are you with the presentation of the results?

- 40 (50%): 5 (Excellent)
- 26 (33%): 4 (Good)
- 11 (14%): 3 (Average)
- 2 (3%): No response
- 1 (1%): 2 (Bad)
- 0 (0%): 1 (Poor)

To summarize, we have received the following grading for Eddy Covariance:

- 83% above average satisfaction for the web interface
- 88% above average satisfaction for the quality of the results
- 79% above average satisfaction for the time to produce the results
- 66% above average satisfaction for the presentation of the results

D3.9 Atmospheric Thematic Services Assessment Report

For Gradient method:

63 responses

What is your level of expertise in the micro-meteorology domain?

- 46 (73%): Pre-grad student
- 9 (14%): Post-grad student
- 5 (8%): Phd in the area
- 3 (5%): Expert
- 0 (0%): No response

How was your experience using our web interface?

- 28 (44%): 5 (Excellent)
- 23 (37%): 4 (Good)
- 11 (17%): 3 (Average)
- 1 (2%): 2 (Bad)
- 0 (0%): No response
- 0 (0%): 1 (Poor)

How satisfied are you with the results?

- 32 (51%): 5 (Excellent)
- 21 (33%): 4 (Good)
- 7 (11%): 3 (Average)
- 3 (5%): 2 (Bad)
- 0 (0%): No response
- 0 (0%): 1 (Poor)

Was the time to produce the results reasonable?

- 33 (52%): 4 (Good)
- 15 (24%): 3 (Average)
- 14 (22%): 5 (Excellent)
- 1 (2%): 2 (Bad)
- 0 (0%): No response
- 0 (0%): 1 (Poor)

How satisfied are you with the presentation of the results?

- 26 (41%): 5 (Excellent)
- 23 (37%): 4 (Good)
- 10 (16%): 3 (Average)

D3.9 Atmospheric Thematic Services Assessment Report

- 2 (3%): No response
- 2 (3%): 2 (Bad)
- 0 (0%): 1 (Poor)

To summarize, we have received the following grading for the Gradient method:

- 81% above average satisfaction for the web interface
- 84% above average satisfaction for the quality of the results
- 76% above average satisfaction for the time to produce the results
- 78% above average satisfaction for the presentation of the results

4.2.2.A2 – ATMO-STRESS

The ATMO-STRESS service user base is composed of 73 total users and 48 users' feedback. These users are divided into different types: internal users (people involved in the design, development and test of the service), and external users from workshops, congresses and webinars (where participants were asked to evaluate the service).

Starting from the second release, feedback was collected by the User feedback forms provided in section 3.2.1. The working group tested the service with students and researchers coming from different domains like:

- Undergraduate students tested the service and gave their feedback on the user-friendliness of ATMO-STRESS during the Geo datathon;
- Master and PhD students from Geological courses gave their feedback about the geological functionality of the service;
- Students and researchers of geological, environmental, and atmospheric domain could also test the service during the NEANIAS Atmospheric Workshops in Athens.

In general, the feedback was positive, especially since the second release until now, where:

- 81% above average satisfaction with the new interface;
- 77% above average satisfaction with the results;
- 91% above average satisfaction with results presentation;
- 88% above average satisfaction with the output formats of the results.

48 responses

What is your level of expertise in stress field recognition domain?

- 17 (35%): None
- 14 (29%): Pre-grad student in this sector
- 9 (19%): PhD student in this sector
- 5 (10%): Expert

D3.9 Atmospheric Thematic Services Assessment Report

- 3 (6%): Post-grad student in this sector

- 0 (0%): No response

On which browser did you use the service?

- 28 (58%): Chrome

- 10 (21%): Safari

- 6 (13%): No response

- 2 (4%): Firefox

- 2 (4%): Other

- 0 (0%): Edge

How user-friendly was the interface?

- 22 (46%): 4 (Good)

- 17 (35%): 5 (Excellent)

- 8 (17%): 3 (Average)

- 1 (2%): 1 (Poor)

- 0 (0%): No response

- 0 (0%): 2 (Bad)

How satisfied are you with the results?

- 26 (54%): 4 (Good)

- 11 (23%): 5 (Excellent)

- 10 (21%): 3 (Average)

- 1 (2%): 2 (Bad)

- 0 (0%): No response

- 0 (0%): 1 (Poor)

Was the time to produce the results reasonable?

- 19 (40%): 4 (Good)

- 15 (31%): 3 (Average)

- 8 (17%): 5 (Excellent)

- 5 (10%): 2 (Bad)

- 1 (2%): 1 (Poor)

- 0 (0%): No response

D3.9 Atmospheric Thematic Services Assessment Report

How satisfied are you with the presentation of the results?

- 28 (58%): 4 (Good)
- 16 (33%): 5 (Excellent)
- 4 (8%): 3 (Average)
- 0 (0%): No response
- 0 (0%): 1 (Poor)
- 0 (0%): 2 (Bad)

How satisfied are you with the output formats of the results (e.g. *.shp, *.kml, *.png, *.json)?

- 24 (50%): 4 (Good)
- 18 (38%): 5 (Excellent)
- 5 (10%): 3 (Average)
- 1 (2%): 1 (Poor)
- 0 (0%): No response
- 0 (0%): 2 (Bad)

If you are not satisfied, in what format would you like your results to be delivered?

- 44 (92%): No response
- pdf,png
- excell - world - pictures
- *.xlsx

Would you recommend the service to your colleagues?

- 41 (85%): Yes
- 6 (13%): No response
- 1 (2%): No

4.2.3.A2 – ATMO-SEISM

The ATMO-SEISM service user base is composed of 29 total users and 12 users' feedback. These users are mostly internal users (people involved in the design, development and test of the service) but also test users (people specifically asked to evaluate the service without prior involvement).

Starting from the second release, feedbacks were collected by the User feedback forms provided in section 3.2.2. Generally, the feedback was uncertain, due to the fact that the

D3.9 Atmospheric Thematic Services Assessment Report

service is not very intuitive because it is designed for people who are experienced in scripting/programming:

- 25% above average satisfaction with the results;
- 75% above average satisfaction with the time to produce the results;
- 10% above average satisfaction with the result presentation;
- 10% above average satisfaction with the output formats of the results.

Analysing the feedback received by each user, the only strongly negative (75% "bad" and 25% "poor") is the one referring to the interface, which is considered not very user-friendly. However, regarding the question "How satisfied are you with the results?" it is possible to observe an equal distribution of "good," "average," and "bad" responses, which means that most users think that the results are adequate despite the complexity of the service. Also, regarding the "Was the time to produce the results reasonable?" question, most feedback is positive (58% "good" and 17% "excellent"). The 60% of users declare that the presentation and output format of the results are "average" satisfactory. The meaning of this result could be due to the improvability of the graphical aspect of the results.

12 responses

What is your level of expertise in the active tectonics domain?

- 7 (58%): PhD student in this sector
- 3 (25%): Expert
- 2 (17%): Post-grad student in this sector
- 0 (0%): No response
- 0 (0%): None
- 0 (0%): Pre-grad student in this sector

How user-friendly was the interface?

- 9 (75%): 2 (Bad)
- 3 (25%): 1 (Poor)
- 0 (0%): No response
- 0 (0%): 3 (Average)
- 0 (0%): 4 (Good)
- 0 (0%): 5 (Excellent)

How satisfied are you with the results?

- 4 (33%): 2 (Bad)
- 4 (33%): 3 (Average)

D3.9 Atmospheric Thematic Services Assessment Report

- 3 (25%): 4 (Good)

- 1 (8%): 1 (Poor)

- 0 (0%): No response

- 0 (0%): 5 (Excellent)

Was the time to produce the results reasonable?

- 7 (58%): 4 (Good)

- 2 (17%): 5 (Excellent)

- 1 (8%): 1 (Poor)

- 1 (8%): 2 (Bad)

- 1 (8%): 3 (Average)

- 0 (0%): No response

How satisfied are you with the presentation of the results?

- 8 (67%): 3 (Average)

- 2 (17%): 2 (Bad)

- 1 (8%): 1 (Poor)

- 1 (8%): 4 (Good)

- 0 (0%): No response

- 0 (0%): 5 (Excellent)

How easy was the download of the results?

- 7 (58%): 2 (Bad)

- 2 (17%): 1 (Poor)

- 2 (17%): 3 (Average)

- 1 (8%): 4 (Good)

- 0 (0%): No response

- 0 (0%): 5 (Excellent)

How satisfied are you with the output format of the results?

- 5 (42%): 2 (Bad)

- 5 (42%): 3 (Average)

- 1 (8%): 1 (Poor)

D3.9 Atmospheric Thematic Services Assessment Report

- 1 (8%): 4 (Good)
- 0 (0%): No response
- 0 (0%): 5 (Excellent)

4.2.4.A3 – ATMO-4CAST

The current ATMO-4CAST service user base is composed of 110 new users and 42 users' feedback (6 for 1st release; 9 for 2nd release; 27 from 3rd release until the moment of this report). These users are divided into different types: internal users (people involved in the conception, design, and development of the service), test users (people specifically asked to evaluate the service without prior involvement), workshops and webinar users (participants were asked to evaluate the service regarding its user-friendliness and potential use).

For both first releases, feedback was gathered from end users by the Test Log template as explained in the section 3.3. Then for the third release, feedback was collected by the User feedback forms provided in section 3.3. We had the opportunity to test this service with students and researchers from different domains. For instance, from the "RAISE YOUR VOICE TOWARDS SUSTAINABILITY" event students from a Master Communication course in University of Aveiro gave their feedback on the UI and user-friendliness of ATMO-4CAST. Then from ATMO-4ALL and NEANIAS Atmospheric Workshops, students and researchers of meteorological, environmental, and atmospheric domain could also test the service. Finally, even after release #3 validations [8], the service counted new users and more feedback was given from internal validations and from NEANIAS Open Innovation Workshop. Overall, the feedback was positive, especially after the third release until now as presented in the summary table presented below (compilation of Google and Next Cloud forms results).

27 responses

Summary Responses

What is your level of expertise in the meteorology / air quality domain?

- 20 (74%): None
- 5 (19%): Pre-grad student in this sector
- 1 (4%): Post-grad student in this sector
- 1 (4%): Expert
- 0 (0%): PhD student in this sector

How was your experience using our web interface?

- 3 (11%): 1 (Poor)
- 2 (7%): 2 (Bad)
- 2 (7%): 3 (Average)
- 10 (37%): 4 (Good)
- 10 (37%): 5 (Excellent)

D3.9 Atmospheric Thematic Services Assessment Report

Which module did you use?

- 5 (19%): 1 (Weather forecast)
- 4 (15%): 2 (Emission simulation)
- 15 (55%): 4 (Air quality simulation)
- 3 (11%): 1 (All)

How satisfied are you with the results?

- 3 (11%): 1 (Poor)
- 1 (4%): 2 (Bad)
- 0 (0%): 3 (Average)
- 11 (41%): 4 (Good)
- 12 (44%): 5 (Excellent)

Was the time to produce the results reasonable?

- 1 (4%): 1 (Poor)
- 3 (11%): 2 (Bad)
- 1 (4%): 3 (Average)
- 9 (33%): 3 (Good)
- 13 (48%): 4 (Excellent)

How satisfied are you with the presentation of the results?

- 3 (11%): 1 (Poor)
- 2 (7%): 2 (Bad)
- 1 (4%): 3 (Average)
- 10 (37%): 3 (Good)
- 11 (41%): 4 (Excellent)

How satisfied are you with the output formats of the results (e.g. *.png, *.json, *.netCDF; *.dmna, *.txt)?

- 1 (4%): 1 (Poor)
- 3 (11%): 2 (Bad)
- 0 (0%): 3 (Average)
- 10 (37%): 3 (Good)
- 12 (44%): 4 (Excellent)

To summarize, we have received the following grading for ATMO-4CAST:

- 74% above average experience using our web interface;
- 85% above average satisfaction with the results;
- 81% above average satisfaction with performance;
- 78% above average satisfaction with results presentation.

D3.9 Atmospheric Thematic Services Assessment Report

The validations enabled the team to improve the UI of the service. For instance, the refreshing of the web service was improved (now happens automatically after a process is completed) and the outputs generated can be visualized in the webservice. Furthermore, ATMO-4CAST is a service that is also being used with real data collect through the NEANIAS Business Cases (BC) (e.g. Smart City BC and GEOInsigth BC). The work done with these Business cases lead to some improvements in the generation of the outputs, which are now given in different formats, thus making the utilisation of the service easy. Additionally, the work done with these Business cases demonstrate that the service may be used outside the Academia and the usefulness of the ATMO-4CAST REST API.

5. Summary

This document presents a final overview on the assessment and evaluation processes of the NEANIAS Atmospheric services. It summarizes the main outcomes of a continuous evaluation of the services from a final user perspective.

Assessment and evaluations processes have been performed for each of the Atmospheric services release cycles (from release #1 to the latest release #3) involving users both internal and external to the NEANIAS consortium. The user base covered a wide range of technical backgrounds, with most users belonging to academic and research institutes and having different levels of expertise (from students to senior scientists).

User feedback has been collected thanks to engagement events using different means, email contact, lectures in universities, webinars, workshops and conferences. This feedback has provided useful insights that have allowed us to progressively improve the services, enhancing availability, stability and user experience until reaching TRL8 and onboarding on EO SC.

References

- [1] NEANIAS WP3 Collaboration, "D3.1: Atmospheric Research Services Report on requirements, Specifications & Software development Plan," NEANIAS, 2020.
- [2] NEANIAS WP3 Collaboration, "D3.2: Atmospheric Research Services Report on Requirements and Specifications," NEANIAS, 2021.
- [3] NEANIAS WP3 Collaboration, "D3.3: Atmospheric Thematic Services Release #1," NEANIAS, 2021.
- [4] NEANIAS WP3 Collaboration, "D3.4: Report on the Developed and Validated Atmospheric Thematic Services (Release #1)," NEANIAS, 2021.
- [5] NEANIAS WP3 Collaboration, "D3.5: Atmospheric Thematic Services Release #2," NEANIAS, 2021.
- [6] NEANIAS WP3 Collaboration, "D3.6: Report on the Developed and Validated Atmospheric Thematic Services (Release #2)," NEANIAS, 2021.
- [7] NEANIAS WP3 Collaboration, "D3.7: Atmospheric Thematic Services Release #3," NEANIAS, 2022.
- [8] NEANIAS WP3 Collaboration, "D3.8: Report on the Developed and Validated Atmospheric Thematic Services (Release #3)," NEANIAS, 2022.
- [9] Lee, J. C., & Angelier, J. (1994). Paleostress trajectory maps based on the results of local determinations: the "Lissage" program. *Computers & Geosciences*, 20(2), 161-191.
- [10] Dias D., Antunes A. P., Tchepel O., 2019. Modelling of emissions and energy use from biofuel fuelled vehicles at urban scale. *Sustainability*, 11(10), 2902.
- [11] Janicke, U. (2014). AUSTAL2000. Program Documentation of Version 2.6. Federal Environmental Agency, Dessau-Roßlau (Germany), Janicke Consulting, Überlingen (Germany), 123 pp.

List of acronyms

Acronym	Description
AAI	Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure
API	Application Programming Interface
EC	European Commission
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EU	European Union
GIS	Geographic Information System
GRIB	General Regularly-distributed Information in Binary form
H2020	Horizon 2020
REST	Representational State Transfer
SMS	Short Message Service
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
UI	User Interface
Vtable	Virtual table
WP	Work Package
WPS	WRF Preprocessing System
WRF	Weather Research & Forecasting Model